

Reduction in Size of Vars by using Different Materials in Generator

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ABSTRACT

In present scenario to achieve refrigeration effect, we have to supply high grade energy which take from shaft which decreases the millage of automobile and increase in cost of fuel. It is not economical to produce refrigeration effect by VCERS .In VARS system we use wasteful energy from exhaust gases of automobile to produce refrigeration effect hence saving cost of fuel.

Optimization of length of tubes of heat exchanger (generator) is done for different material like stainless steel, aluminium, copper to achieve 1TR Refrigeration effect. Inlet temperature of generator is 25°C and COP of refrigerator is 0.7.

KEYWORDS: COP (coefficient of performance), VARS (vapour absorption refrigeration system), VCERS (vapour compression refrigeration system), TR (Tonne of refrigeration)

INTRODUCTION

Comparison between VCERS and VARS

VCERS	VARS
1. In VCERS we use compressor that uses hybrid energy in the form of work.	1. In VARS we use generator, Absorber and pump that uses low grade energy, in form energy
2. The refrigerating effect or refrigerating capacity decreases with lower evaporator pressure	2. Very little effect is seen In the refrigerating capacity with lowering evaporator pressure.
3. VCERS doesn't work at partial load	3. Varying load doesn't affect performance of VCERS
4. Refrigerant and Hydrocarbons CFCs hydrochlorofluorocarbon's	4. Ammonia or water can be used as Refrigerant with proper absorber.

Simple vapour absorption system

The continuous increase in the cost and demand for energy has led to more research and development to utilize available energy resources efficiently by minimizing waste energy with reference to [1] Replacing the electrical energy with solar energy will reduce the consumption of high grade electrical energy. Also the replacement of compression system with absorption system eliminates the energy consumption by compressors [2] In the context diesel engine exhaust heat utilization has the potential to reduce the consumption of fossil fuels and reduce the release of greenhouse gases, significant waste heat recovery technologies have been developed to recover exhaust heat and turn it into useful energy such as electricity [5] To reduce

the Ozone depletion many refrigerant has been banned and due to increase in global warming it is necessary to have an alternate source which will be reliable and meet the future requirements in cars[7]

Engine specification of Toyota Innova Crysta

Fuel type: Diesel
 Engine Displacement: 2393cc
 Torque:343Nm@1400rpm
 Power: 148BHP@3400rpm

System Description

Concentration	kg of NH3/Kg of solution	Enthalpy
Strong solution leaving absorber	.421	30
Weak solution leaving generator(x2)	.375	340
Vapour leaving generator	.945	1870
Liquid leaving condenser	.945	470
Vapour leaving evaporator(x1)	.945	1388

- m1 = mass of strong solution leaving absorber
- m2' =mass of weak solution leaving generator
- m1' =mass of vapour leaving evaporator
- X1 =mole fraction of strong solution
- X2' =mole fraction of weak solution
- X1' =mole fraction of vapour leaving evaporator
- Cp = Specific heat capacity of aqua ammonia
- Tce =exhaust temperature of aqua ammonia
- Tci =inlet temperature of aqua ammonia
- Tavg =average temperature of aqua ammonia
- ma =mass flow rate of air
- mf =mass flow rate of fluid
- mex = mass flow rate of exhaust
- Cpex = specific heat capacity at exhaust
- Di =inner dia of tube
- Do =outer dia of tube
- μg =dynamic viscosity of exhaust gases
- Kg =Thermal conductivity of exhaust gases
- Ug =velocity of exhaust gases

$$U = \text{velocity of exhaust gases} = U_g \times \frac{S_t}{S_t - d_0}$$

$$Re = \frac{U \times d_0}{\mu_g}$$

$$Nu = \frac{h_o \times d_0}{k_g} = \text{Nusselt Number}$$

h_o =convective heat transfer coefficient

For Aqua-Ammonia

- μ =Dynamic viscosity of aqua ammonia
- k =Thermal conductivity of aqua ammonia

$$Pr = \frac{\mu \times C_p}{k_g} = \text{Prandtl number}$$

$$Re = m \times \frac{D_{eq}}{\mu}$$

$$Nu = .06 \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_v} \right)^{.28} \times (Re)^{.87} \times (Pr)^{.4}$$

hi =convective heat transfer coefficient for inner tube

$$\frac{1}{U_o} = \frac{1}{h_i} \times \frac{d_o}{d_i} + \frac{d_o}{2k_g} \ln \left(\frac{d_o}{d_i} \right) + \frac{1}{h_o}$$

Thermodynamic Analysis

$$m_1 = m_2' + m_1'$$

$$m_1' \times (\text{Latentheat}) = 1TR$$

$$m_1' = .00424 \text{ kg / s}$$

$$m_1 x_1 = m_2' x_2 + m_1' x_1'$$

$$m_2' = .0483 \text{ kg / s}$$

$$m_1 = .052539 \text{ kg / s}$$

$$C_{pD} = 3.8927 + 95.779 / (133 - T)$$

$$T = C$$

$$C_p = J / g^\circ C$$

$$T_{ce} = 42^\circ C$$

$$T_{ci} = 25^\circ C$$

$$T_{avg} = 33.5^\circ C$$

$$C_p = 4.8553 \text{ kJ / Kg }^\circ C$$

$$\Delta T = 17^\circ C$$

$$\dot{m}_a = \rho * V * \eta * (N / 2)$$

$$= .02505977 \text{ Kg / s}$$

$$\text{AirFuelratio} = 14 \text{ to } 20$$

$$\frac{\dot{m}_a}{m_f} = 15$$

$$\dot{m}_f = 1.737318 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg / sec}$$

$$m_{ex} = 0.0277971 \text{ kg / sec}$$

$$m_a \times C_p \times \Delta T = m_{ex} \times C_{pex} \times \Delta T_{ex}$$

$$T_{hi} - T_{he} = \Delta T_{ex} = 141.82$$

$$T_{he} = 1442.78^\circ C$$

Results and discussion

$$d_i = 28mm$$

$$LMDT = 174$$

$$T_{avg} = 488.69k$$

$$\mu_g = 2.6577 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Ns/m}^2$$

$K_g = 0.36314W/mk$
 $Pr = .80805$
 $U_g = 5.36248m/s$
 $Re = 14646.8$
 $Nu = 123.17$
 $h_o = 149.092634W/m^2k$
 $\mu = 900\mu Pa.sec = 9 \times 10^{-4} Pa.sec$
 $K = .504W/mk$
 $Pr = 8.0922$
 $Re = 2654.553$
 $Nu = 892.08$
 $h_i = 17204.4W/m^2k$
 $U_o = 147.611W/m^2k$
 $QG = U_o \times A \times LMTD$
 $A = .168m^2$
 $A = \pi DL$
 $L = 1.783m$

ON THE BASIS OF THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

S. no.	Materials	Temp(°C)	Thermal Conductivity(w/mk)
1	Aluminium	124.595	239.92
2	Stainless Steel	124.595	15.53
3	Beryllium	124.595	162.1
4	Chromium	124.595	87.44

S. no.	Material	Melting Point(°C)	Length of Tube(m)
1	Stainless Steel	1340	1.8
2	Aluminium	660.3	1.783
3	Berilium	1287	1.7833
4	Chromium	1907	1.785

CONCLUSION

In present times stainless steel tubes are used for Aqua Ammonia refrigerant (NH3-H2O) for heat transfer in case of steel length of tube is more compared other materials like as Aluminium, Beryllium and chromium which have the same heat transfer capacity.

For low temperature we use Aluminium, and for the high temperature we use chromium to replace the stainless steel which has high melting point up to 1907oC-

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